

Ink-Jet Printed Electro-Adhesive Grippers

Yi Chen
STIIMA Institute
National Research Council
Milan, Italy
Yi.Chen@stiima.cnr.it

Nicolò Berdozzi
DIN Department
University of Bologna
Bologna, Italy
nicolo.berdozzi2@unibo.it

Irene Fassi
STIIMA Institute
National Research Council
Milan, Italy
Irene.Fassi@stiima.cnr.it

Vincenzo Parenti Castelli
DIN Department
University of Bologna
Bologna, Italy
vincenzo.parenti@unibo.it

Lorenzo Molinari Tosatti
STIIMA Institute
National Research Council
Milan, Italy
Lorenzo.MolinariTosatti@stiima.cnr.it

Rocco Vertechy*
DIN Department
University of Bologna
Bologna, Italy
rocco.vertechy@unibo.it

Abstract—Retention actions are better suited than simple compression forces in applications requiring the grasping of objects that are fragile, compliant or of irregular shape. One of the principles that can be used to create a retention action between two mating surfaces is electro-adhesion. In addition to provide an overview on the major findings reported so far by different research group in the world, this work describes the preliminary results on the development of electro-adhesive devices manufactured by ink-jet printing and blade coating that have been obtained at the SAIMA Laboratory (namely, the Laboratory for Innovative Sensors and Actuators for Advanced Manufacturing), established by a research agreement between the STIIMA Institute of the Italian National Research Council (CNR) and the University of Bologna (UNIBO).

Keywords—*electro-adhesion, ink-jet printing, shear stress*

I. INTRODUCTION

Several techniques exist nowadays for grasping an object. In applications where fragile, compliant or variable shape bodies need to be held, a retention action is typically preferred to a compression force. Methods for generating retention actions between two mating surfaces can be based on a variety of technologies, such as vacuum suction, magneto-adhesion and electro-adhesion [1]. In the latter, prehension forces are obtained by exploiting the electrostatic attraction of charged electrical conductors and polarized dielectrics, and can be augmented by mechanical friction in the direction tangent to the mating surfaces. As no perfect dielectric really exists in nature and since some irregular airgap is always present between the mating surfaces, the exact working principle governing the response of practical electro-adhesive devices (EADs) is not well established so far, and coarse models with limited accuracy only exist for estimating the retention forces produced by them [1-3]. Despite the complicated physics and although the resulting retention actions might be lower than those attained by vacuum suction and magneto-adhesion, EADs feature the following advantages [1-2]: electrical activation with low power consumption, as they are electrostatic capacitors; minimal effect to the adhered objects, as the electro-adhesive actions extinguish very quickly away from the mating surfaces; applicability to a wide range of solid materials that include electrical conductors, dielectrics and porous media; operation in different environments such as in air (and other gases), liquids and vacuum; intrinsic flexibility that enables to automatically adapt their shape to that of the object to be grasped; prehension performances that are rather independent of device size. In addition, electro-adhesive devices can be manufactured to be lightweight, compact and soft, as well as conformed to almost any shape and size.

This work first summarizes the developments attained in recent years in the field of EADs, by particularly focusing on target applications and attained performances. Then, it describes the results of an on-going research activity performed at the CNR-UNIBO SAIMA Laboratory that is devoted to the fabrication, testing and application of EADs in the field of robotics and automated production systems.

Figure 1: Electro-Adhesive Device (EAD) cross-section (a) and electrode strip array partial front-view (b)

II. CURRENT STATUS OF ELECTRO-ADHESIVE DEVICES

A typical layout of an EAD is depicted in Figure 1 [4-9]. It features a layered structure in which an array of electrode strips, with alternating charge polarity (represented in red and grey), are encapsulated within two dielectric layers. The lower dielectric layer (depicted in yellow) is the one in contact with the object to be grasped; it dominantly affects the resulting retention action mostly through its thickness, electrical permittivity, resistivity, and dielectric strength. The upper dielectric layer (depicted in cyan) insulates the electrodes from the environment, increases the breakdown voltage of the overall device (hence, the maximal retention action) and may be used to bond the EAD to a host structure. As regards to applications, EADs have been proposed for the grasping of soft and fragile objects, optical and electro-optical micro-components and for increasing the traction of mobile and climbing robots [1-9]. In these applications, the adhesive shear stress (ASS) is a key performance index, which indicates the limiting tangential force per unit of active EAD prehension surface that can be applied to the adhered object and not to be exceeded to prevent sliding. In terms of measured ASS: in [4], planar EADs demonstrated about 2 kPa for the grasping of drywall, paper and dry concrete, 4 kPa for glass, 5.5 kPa for finished wood and 14 kPa for steel; in [5], planar EADs with an active area of around 56 cm² demonstrated less than 0.7 kPa when grasping drywall, melamine, PMMA, and concrete, about 1.2 kPa for glass and about 3.2 for steel; in [6], a planar EAD with an active area of around 100 cm² demonstrated about 2 kPa when grasping a steel plate; in [7], planar EADs with different electrode patterns with an active area of around 20 cm² demonstrated

*Corresponding Author

11 kPa when grasping drywall; in [8], a dielectric elastomer actuated gripper integrating two EAD pads, each featuring an active area of 1cm^2 , demonstrated 35 kPa for the grasping of paper attached to a polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) substrate; in [9], a soft pneumatic gripper with an EAD patch featuring an active area of 71.4cm^2 demonstrated 1.4 kPa when grasping a cellulose diacetate film.

Although these results have been obtained on samples with different manufacturing procedures, materials and electrode patterns, they provide the order of magnitude for the ASS that can currently be achieved by practical EADs. Among the different factors, the specific process that is employed for EAD manufacturing is the one that severely limits device performance and reliability, the most critical part being electrode patterning on the dielectric layers. In this regard, in the reported works electrode realization has been performed via etching [6,7], laser ablation combined with plasma bonding [8] and soft lithography [9].

Figure 2: EAD manufactured at CNR-UNIBO SAIMA Laboratory via ink-jet printing and blade coating

III. SAIMA ELECTRO-ADHESIVE DEVICES: MANUFACTURING APPROACH AND PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Since November 2018, a new facility and related processing procedures have been set-up at the CNR-UNIBO SAIMA Laboratory for the manufacturing of EADs featuring different dielectric/electrode materials, shapes and sizes (namely, from millimeter to decimeter scale). The considered fabrication process employs blade coating for dielectric layer deposition and ink-jet printing for electrode patterning. In particular, blade coating has been selected since it is a simple and fast process enabling the deposition of thin films with high thickness uniformity; ink-jet printing has been selected due to its non-contact, mask-less and master-less nature, which enables the easy patterning of electrode traces featuring good accuracy and repeatability, as well as for its suitability to a wide range of production scales, from prototyping to large-scale industrial production.

A fully functional planar EAD, with an active area of 9.6cm^2 ($L = 24\text{mm}$ and $H = 40\text{mm}$), which has been manufactured at SAIMA Laboratory is shown in Figure 2. Referring to the schematic of Figure 1: the bottom dielectric layer is made of Kapton and has a thickness $h_2 = 25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$; electrodes strips are printed with a silver nano-particle ink, with a width $w = 400\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and a gap $g = 300\text{ }\mu\text{m}$; the upper dielectric layer is made of silicone elastomer and has a thickness $h_1 = 400\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3: Schematic of the test-bench employed for measuring the adhesive shear stress (ASS) produced by the EAD as function of the electric potential difference (V) applied to the electrodes

To assess the ASS of the manufactured EAD, an experimental testing set-up has also been developed according to the

schematic shown in Figure 3. In the set-up, the EAD sample is kept fixed and a thin film (depicted in green) with desirable thickness and material composition is used as the object to be grasped. The thin film is movable and pulled in the direction parallel to the active surface of the EAD through a load-cell mounted on a linear guide, which enables the measurement of the tangential component of the limiting retention force as function of the electric potential difference (voltage, V) applied to the EAD electrodes.

Figure 4: Experimental performance of the manufactured EAD when grasping a $25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick Kapton film: ASS vs applied voltage

Use of this set-up for the characterization of the EAD shown in Figure 2 when grasping a thin film of Kapton with $25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thickness provides the results reported in Figure 4. As it can be seen, the ASS generated by the EAD strongly depends on the voltage applied across the electrodes and, for the considered device and grasped substrate, it achieves a maximum of about 10 kPa. Although this recorded value is already adequate for many practical applications, far better results are expected in the following cases: 1) the same EAD is used to grasp objects with higher thickness and made of different materials; 2) the EAD is optimized in terms of constitutive materials, shape and size. All these aspects are currently under investigation at SAIMA Laboratory.

REFERENCES

- [1] G.J. Monkman, "An Analysis of Astrictive Prehension," *Int. J. Robot. Res.*, vol. 16, n. 1, pp. 1–10, 1997.
- [2] G. J. Monkman, P. M. Taylor, e G. J. Farnworth, "Principles of electroadhesion in clothing robotics," *Int. J. Cloth. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 1, n. 3, pp. 14–20, 1989.
- [3] C. Cao, X. Sun, Y. Fang, Q.-H. Qin, A. Yu, X.-Q. Feng, "Theoretical model and design of electroadhesive pad with interdigitated electrodes," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 89, pp. 485–491, 2016.
- [4] H. Prahlad, R. Pelrine, S. Stanford, J. Marlow, R. Kornbluh, "Electroadhesive robots—wall climbing robots enabled by a novel, robust, and electrically controllable adhesion technology," in 2008 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation, pp. 3028–3033, Pasadena (CA), 19–23 May 2008.
- [5] J.P.D. Tellez, J. Krahn, C. Menon, "Characterization of electro-adhesives for robotic applications," in *Proc. of 2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics*, pp. 1867–1872, Karon Beach (Thailand), 7–11 December 2011.
- [6] L. Savioli, G. Sguotti, A. Francesconi, F. Branz, J. Krahn, C. Menon, "Morphing electroadhesive interface to manipulate uncooperative objects," in *Proc. SPIE 9061, Sensors and Smart Structures Technologies for Civil, Mechanical, and Aerospace Systems*, p. 906129, San Diego (CA), 10–13 March 2014.
- [7] D. Ruffatto, J. Shah, M. Spenko, "Increasing the adhesion force of electrostatic adhesives using optimized electrode geometry and a novel manufacturing process," *J. Electrostat.*, vol. 72, n. 2, pp. 147–155, 2014.
- [8] J. Shintake, S. Rosset, B. Schubert, D. Floreano, H. Shea, "Versatile Soft Grippers with Intrinsic Electroadhesion Based on Multifunctional Polymer Actuators," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 28, n. 2, pp. 231–238, 2016.
- [9] J. Guo, K. Elgencidy, C. Xiang, N. Lohse, L. Justham, e J. Rossiter, "Soft pneumatic grippers embedded with stretchable electroadhesion," *Smart Mater. Struct.*, vol. 27, n. 5, p. 055006, 2018.